

EFFECTIVENESS OF PHYSIOTHERAPY IN BURNS: A CASE STUDY.

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Abstract

A single case study design was used to investigate the effectiveness of physiotherapy in burns. Total area of burn was assessed using Wallace rule of nine and Lund and Browder's chart. Range of motion for the involved joints was measured by goniometer while muscle strength was assessed using modified research council (MRC) scale. Depression & anxiety status was measured using The Burn's Depression Checklist & burns anxiety inventory respectively. Assessment was taken at 2 time points during the study, at baseline and after 2 weeks of physiotherapy treatment. The patient received two sessions of physiotherapy treatment per day. The physiotherapy treatment resulted in improvement in ROM, strength & reduced depression and anxiety level. It also had great contribution in prevention of deformities and contractures. Although single case study design limits generalization of the results, it does provide evidence of the beneficial response obtained by use of physiotherapy management in burns patients.

Keywords: Burn, ROM, Strength, Deformities, Contractures.

Introduction

Burns patient belong to a heterogeneous population, due to a wide variation in age, mechanism of injury, depth and site of burn and different co-morbidities¹. Burn is the second most common cause of death. The mortality rate due to full or partial burns goes up to 15.1 per year per 100,000 populations, in rural districts, also it constitutes for almost 23.3% of all medico legal deaths². The Primary tissue loss in a burn injury occurs as a result of the protein denaturation, which is secondary to thermal injury, chemical burns, electrical burn, friction or ultraviolet radiation-induced skin abrasions. After their occurrence, the process of tissue healing is rapidly followed by activation of toxic inflammatory mediators, especially found in the perfused subsurface. Other causes are the oxidants and proteases which further damage skin and capillary endothelial cells, leading to ischemic tissue necrosis³. One of the most commonly followed classification systems, uses the depth of injury to categorize the severity of the burn. The classification of burns includes 1) Superficial thickness burn 2) Superficial partial thickness burn 3) Deep partial thickness and 4) Full thickness burn^{4,5}. Burn injuries are also classified by the size & its dimensions. Wallace rule of nine⁶ and Lund & Browder's diagrams⁷ provide a systematic method for calculating. It helps to calculate the total Body Surface Area (TBSA) burned area for both adults and children. Burn injuries exhibit varied physical and psychological rehabilitation challenges for the individual. To restore the independent function of the patient is the ultimate goal of rehabilitation & to enhance functional abilities, the treatment should focus on all aspects of the

human life such as strength, gaining Range of motion/movement, mobility and self-care, re-integration into family and community, with adaptive psychosocial responses, and self-determination. Physical Therapy is individualized according to the burn location, depth, and size as well as other associated injuries or complications. Such as anxiety, depression and psychological problems may interfere with compliance to various rehabilitation measures. Therefore, the objective of this study was to evaluate the effectiveness of physical therapy in burns.

Method :

2.1 Research Design: A single case study design was used to achieve the objectives of this project.

2.2 Subject: Subject was a 40 years old female with Superficial partial thickness burn at right upper limb, trunk, medial aspect of left upper limb & buttock, thigh, calf of right lower limb. Total burn surface area was 56.5% according to Wallace rule of nine & 56% according to Lund and Browder's chart with zone of coagulative necrosis. At initial assessment, patient presented with burning pain, reduce range of motion and muscle strength of all muscle groups of bilateral upper extremities and right lower extremity, and also difficulty in independent sitting, standing and walking.

Examination revealed following findings:

On observation:

3.1.1 Depth of burn : Superficial partial thickness burn^{4,5}.

3.1.2 Total Surface Body Area : 56.5% according to Wallace rule of nine & 56 %according to Lund & Browder's chart^{6,7}.(appendix 1)

3.1.3Zones of burn : Zone of coagulative necrosis & zone of stasis.

3.2 On physical examination :

3.2.1 Range of motion : Reduced range of motion of all joints of bilateral upper extremities and right lower extremity.

3.2.2 Manual muscle testing according to modified research council scale: Reduced muscle strength of all muscle groups of bilateral upper extremities and right lower extremity.

3.2.3 Pinch strength(pulp to pulp) : Pinch meter was used to measure the pinch strength which was reduced.

3.3 Psychological impact :

It was measured by depression checklist⁹ & The Burns Anxiety Inventory¹⁰. Mild depression & moderate anxiety was found (as shown in results)

Physiotherapy intervention :

A burn is a very common injury and can have a significant impact upon the individual's functional ability. Therefore Physiotherapy is vital in minimizing / preventing impairments to body functions and structures and restoring full independence. The therapeutic range of motion exercises, continuous stretching, proper positioning was designed to treat the patient with burn. The prophylactic chest physiotherapy was given which included incentive spirometry 10 repetitions twice daily to prevent chest complications. Range of motion exercises for both upper and lower extremities were started followed by 10 repetitions of static stretching for shoulder flexors, extensors & abductors, flexors & extensors of elbow, wrist, knee joints. Various functional activities along with stretching were encouraged to improve the strength and mobility of hand. Physiotherapy treatment was coordinated with analgesics. Then we end up the physiotherapy treatment with proper positioning to prevent contracture^{4,8,11}. (appendix 2).

Results :

When the patient received the physiotherapy treatment for 2 weeks she achieved significant functional gains with an improvement in the ROM (Table no. 1), Pinch strength (Table no. 2) with improved muscle strength from grade -3 to 4 of all muscle groups of bilateral upper extremities and right lower extremity. At the end of 2 weeks of physiotherapy intervention patient could sit & walk independently. There were no evidences of contracture formation. As initially patient had mild depression and moderate anxiety which was reduced along with the treatment.(Table no. 3) At the time of discharge we had given advice to continue exercises with proper positioning.

Table no. 1 :ROM before and after physiotherapy intervention.

ROM	Right		Left	
	Before	After	Before	After
Shoulder flexion	40	68	65	110
Abduction	65	90	70	112
Medial rotation	5	25	60	60
Lateral rotation	10	50	70	70
Elbow flexion	25-80	15-96	32-90	10-115
Extension	80-25	96-15	90-32	115-10
Supination	20	62	90	90
Pronation	15	65	80	80
Wrist flexion	5	54	85	85
Extension	8	45	62	62
Radial deviation	5	10	10	10
Ulnar deviation	10	15	28	28
Hip flexion	35	80	100	100
Abduction	5	20	28	28
Knee flexion	20-70	10-92	0-120	0-120
Extension	70-20	92-10	120-0	120-0

Table no.2 : Pinch strength before and after physiotherapy intervention

	Right		Left	
	Before	After	Before	After
Pinch strength (pulp to pulp)	2 pounds	6 pounds	8 pounds	8 pounds

Table no.3: Psychological impact of burn before and after physiotherapy intervention.

	Before	After
Burns Depression Checklist (out of 100)	17 (mild)	9 (normal)
Burns Anxiety Inventory (Out of 99)	30 (moderate)	11 (mild)

Discussion :

According to assessment, it was the case of 56% burns. Rehabilitation is an essential and integral part of burn treatment. The term 'Burns Rehabilitation' incorporates the physical, psychological and social aspects of care and it is common for burn patients to experience difficulties in one or all of these areas following a burn injury. The aim of burn rehabilitation is to minimize the adverse effects caused by the injury in terms of maintaining range of movement, minimizing contracture development and impact of scarring, maximizing functional ability, maximizing psychological wellbeing, maximizing social integration⁸.

Fiona Procter in their study "rehabilitation of burn" stated that deconditioning and impaired physical condition is a common complication following burn injury due to the hyper-metabolic response seen in severe burn coupled with the effects of pain and prolonged bed rest. High metabolism and poor oral intake associated with severe burn injury exacerbate muscle wasting if there is no physical stimulus. So range of motion exercises were performed for all joints affected by burns¹¹.

Anti-contracture positioning was started from the first day as the positioning is important to influence tissue length by limiting or inhibiting loss of ROM secondary to the development of scar tissue⁴. Stiffness is common in burn patients both in joints effected by a burn injury and in other joints when immobilized for periods of time. Stretching of affected joints several times a day to their maximum functional range, in conjunction with a splinting regime appears to help elongate the scar tissue maintaining ROM^{4,8}.

Conclusion:

This study has documented that the physiotherapy interventions leads to improvement in range of motion, muscle strength along with functional improvement in case burn.

Conflict of Interest: The author's report no conflict of interest.

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Appendix no. 1 :

Wallace rule of nine : 56.5 % & Lund & Browder's chart : 56%

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